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D3.2 Data Management and APIs for Data Collection v2

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable is a demonstrator of the Policy and Data Management component in AI4PublicPolicy developed in work package 3, AI-based Reusable and Interoperable Policies. This component was developed in the context of task 3.1 Collection and Management of Public Policy Datasets. The deliverable presents the second and final version of the component. The Policy and Data Management component is used for uploading datasets into the AI4PublicPolicy platform as well as for the definition and management of policies. The datasets and the policies will be exploited by the AI analysis tools in AI4PublicPolicy. The datasets and policies are stored in EGI DataHub. Current stored data and policies come from the different pilots in AI4PP however, the Policy and Data Management component is able to deal with other data, simply providing its schema. The Data Management can deal with Big Data by running in a distributed environment.

The deliverable presents the usage, architecture, and APIs of the component. The Data Management component software can be deployed as a standalone component that uses EGI DataHub platform as storage. This component can be downloaded as an application for the Linux environment.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realisation of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organisation transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercialising the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform. The structure of the project in work packages is presented in Figure 1. This deliverable is the result of the work done in task T3.1 in Work Package 3.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP3

WP3 “AI-based Reusable and Interoperable Policies” is a central work package in the AI4PublicPolicy platform. This work package provides the necessary components for: 1) enabling data collection and management of different types of datasets 2) Make data usable through interoperability techniques. 3) Enable reuse of datasets, policies, and AI models. 3) Contribute to openness through an open catalogue of policies, datasets and AI models.

1.3 Objective of the Deliverable

The main objective of this deliverable is to describe the final version of the software for the Policy and Data Management component developed in the context of task T3.1 Collection and Management of Public Policy Datasets. This software is in charge of the definition, collection and storage of the datasets from the different pilots in AI4PublicPolicy datastore as well as the policies. The deliverable describes the architecture of the component, its subcomponents, how it is used and how the software is distributed. The main difference with the previous version of this deliverable is the integration with EGI DataHub, the definition of a web interface, a REST API, the separation of the datasets according to a set of predefined areas and a detailed description of the component architecture.

1.4 Structure of the Deliverable

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the Policy and Data Management component in the context of the AI4PublicPolicy project. Section 3 is devoted to the description of the different interfaces provided by the Policy and Data Management component. Section 4 presents the architecture of the component and its implementation, describing the subcomponents of the Policy and Data Management, and the corresponding sequence diagrams. Section 5 describes the Policy and Data Management software distribution. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions.

2 Collection and Management of Public Policy Datasets

The Policy and Data Management component (Data Management in Figure 2) is in charge of the collection and management of the policies and datasets from different stakeholders in the AI4PublicPolicy platform. The dataset management component loads and stores the data and policies to be analysed by the Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME). Data can be collected from diverse data source types and in different formats including data at-rest and streaming data. The data is stored in the AI4PublicPolicy storage placed at EGI DataHub.

Figure 2. AI4PublicPolicy architecture main components

3 Policy and Data Management Interface

The Policy and Data Management component provides two different user interfaces, the web interface and the REST API interfaces. Users can select the one that is more suitable/intuitive for them. The REST APIs are also used for the integration of this component with other components in the AI4PublicPolicy architecture, for instance with the VPME.

3.1 Web Interface

A web interface was developed to ease the use of the component for non-technical users that upload datasets in the platform or define policies. All interfaces have been implemented using HTML and JavaScript. There are three main interfaces: datasets, policies and the AI models interfaces. Datasets and policies are grouped by area (Pilot): *Noise Management, Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance, Citizens and Business Services Optimisation, and Management and Optimisation of City Resources and Energy Management.*

Dataset schema definition

This interface is used to define the schema of a new type of dataset. That is, the format and type of the elements a dataset have. This interface is used only when a new pilot is added, or new types of data are generated. Figure 3 shows the Dataset Definition interface- which is a form that internally is converted into a JSON object with the schema defined in Section 4.2.2. The user selects an area, provides the dataset name, selects the type of files in the dataset (csv, json, geo-json, xlsx or image), and if it is an image, the format of the image has to be indicated (jpg, png,...), the description of the dataset, the owner, the language (English, Italian, Greek, Portuguese and Bulgarian), and the names of the fields of the dataset set if the dataset type is different to image. For each field of the dataset, a name, type, description and default value have to be provided.

The screenshot shows the 'Dataset Definition' form on the AI4PublicPolicy website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'Navbar', 'Home', 'Policy', 'Datasets', and 'AI Model', along with a search bar. The main heading is 'Dataset Definition' with a sub-heading 'Register a new dataset'. The form includes several input fields: 'Area' (a dropdown menu), 'Dataset Name' (a text input), 'Source Type' (a dropdown menu with 'csv' selected), and 'Image format' (a dropdown menu). Below these are a 'Dataset description' text area and an 'Owner' text input. A 'Language' dropdown menu is set to 'English'. The 'Dataset fields definition' section contains a table with one row labeled 'Field #1' and a column header 'DEFINE EACH FIELD OF THE DATASET'. An 'Add field' button is located to the right of the table. A 'Submit' button is at the bottom left of the form. The footer of the page contains the European Union logo, funding information, copyright notice, and social media links.

Figure 3. Dataset definition

List of Datasets

Once the dataset is defined its definition can be seen in the Datasets interface as shown in Figure 4. The user selects one of the areas (*Citizens and Business Services Optimisation* in the figure), and all previously defined datasets are shown with a description and the language of the data. When clicking on the dataset description (*Accidents* in the figure), the list of available datasets files is shown (*Incidenti 2021.xlsx*). A dataset is downloaded by clicking on it.

Figure 4. Datasets Interface

Uploading a Dataset

The user can upload files in two different ways: using the Dataset Management interface, or uploading the dataset through the EGI DataHub interface, presented in Section 3.2. The Dataset Management interface in Figure 5 provides a form where the user selects the area, the dataset definition, and the endpoint where the dataset file to be uploaded is available. Then, clicking on the submit button the Dataset Management component downloads the file and stores it into a EGI DataHub folder that keeps all the files for that dataset.

The screenshot shows the 'Dataset Management' page of the AI4PublicPolicy website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'Navbar', 'Home', 'Policy', 'Datasets', and 'AI Model'. A search bar is located on the right side of the navigation bar. Below the navigation bar is the AI4PublicPolicy logo. The main heading is 'Dataset Management'. Underneath, there is a sub-heading 'Upload a dataset file from an endpoint'. The form consists of three main sections: 'Area' with a dropdown menu showing '-- Select an area --'; 'Dataset' with a dropdown menu showing 'Select the area'; and 'Endpoint' with a text input field. Below the input fields, there is a small text instruction: 'Indicate the http endpoint where your dataset file is available.' At the bottom of the form is a blue 'Submit' button. The footer of the page is black and contains the European Union logo, funding information from the Horizon 2020 programme, social media icons, and copyright information.

Figure 5. Dataset Management

Policy Definition

The policy interfaces are similar to the dataset ones. Figure 6 shows the policy definition interface where a new policy is defined. First of all, the area of the policy must be selected. Then, the name of the policy, the owner, the description, the policy objective, KPIs and metadata information must be provided. The datasets to be used in the policy are added in the datasets section of the form. This section contains a drop-down widget with the datasets available for the selected area. By clicking on the submit button the policy is stored into the database.

Navbar Home Policy ▾ Datasets ▾ AI Model ▾

Policy Definition

Register a new policy

Area

Policy Name Owner

Policy description

Objective

Policy Datasets
SELECT THE DATASETS TO BE USED IN THIS POLICY

Dataset

Indicate the dataset to be used in the policy from the available ones. This field can be empty and be filled latter.

Policy KPIs definition
DEFINE THE KPIS OF THE POLICY

KPI #1

Policy Metadata definition
DEFINE THE METADATA OF THE POLICY

Metadata #1

Figure 6. Policy Definition Interface

List of Policies

Once a policy is defined, it is available in the policies interface (Figure 7). Clicking on a given area (*Citizens and Business Services Optimisation* in the figure) all stored policies with their name, description, and associated datasets are listed. Clicking in the *More Information* button the objectives, KPIs and metadata are shown (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Policies Interface

Figure 8. Policies Description Interface

Policy Update

Figure 9 shows how to update the information of a policy through the web interface. Selecting the area, a policy drop down field with the policies stored for that area is shown. Selecting a policy, all the information associated to the policy is shown. The user can update any field and submit the changes.

Area

-- Select an area --

Policy

Select the policy

Owner

Policy description

Objective

Policy Datasets

DATASETS USED IN THE POLICY

Add Dataset

Policy KPIs definition

KPIS OF THE POLICY

Add KPI

Policy Metadata definition

METADATA OF THE POLICY

Add Metadata

Submit

Figure 9. Policy Update Interface

AI Models Interface

The AI Models interface presents the AI Models defined for the different areas. Selecting the area, a drop down menu with all the policies stored is shown. When the user selects a given policy, the AI Models associated to that policy are listed (Figure 10).

Figure 10. AI Models Interface

A video tutorial was recorded showing how to use the Policy and Data Management component web interface, this video is available at <https://ai4publicpolicy.eu/ai4publicpolicy-dataset-and-policy-management-demonstration/>.

3.2 EGI DataHub Interface

Another way to upload a dataset is using the EGI DataHub file system interface as depicted in Figure 11. When the dataset is defined, internally the data management component creates a folder where datasets are stored. This interface is similar to any file system interface and therefore it is very intuitive for any type of users. Figure 11 shows the folder created for the *Energy Management Policies Pilot* area and the *CITY SENSORS* dataset schema. A user can log in into AI4PublicPolicy space and access that folder. The user can drag and drop the dataset or use the upload button on the right side of the interface.

Figure 11. EGI Datahub

3.3 REST API

Two different REST API have been developed to interact with the Policy and Data Management component, one for data management and other one for the policies. These APIs can be used by programs from pilots to automatically upload data and are also used internally by the AI4PublicPolicy platform to manage policies and datasets.

3.4 Data Management REST API

The dataset management component provides a REST API with all operations needed for data management. The definition of REST API with the Swagger is shown in Figure 12. Seven operations allow users to define, update, delete and read dataset schemas, and store datasets associated to a given schema.

datasetManagement Show/Hide List Operations Expand Operations

DELETE	/datasetManagement/schema/{schema_id}	Deletes a particular schema and all its datasets
GET	/datasetManagement/schema/{schema_id}	Returns the information of a particular schema
PUT	/datasetManagement/schema/{schema_id}	Updates a dataset schema
POST	/datasetManagement/schema	Defines a new dataset schema
GET	/datasetManagement/dataset	Download an image or file from DataHub
PUT	/datasetManagement/dataset	Collects a new dataset
GET	/datasetManagement/dataLake	Show a list of available datasets for a particular pilot and dataset name
GET	/datasetManagement/schemas	Returns the information of all the stored schemas

[BASE URL: /ai4pp] UPGRADE {...}

Figure 12. Dataset Management REST API

The operations are:

- POST /datasetManagement/schema
Creates a new dataset schema. A JSON object must be provided with the schema of the dataset (defined in Section 4.2.2). Each schema has a unique integer identifier, *schema_id*.
- PUT /datasetManagement/schema/{schema_id}
Updates of an existing dataset schema. The *schema_id* and a JSON object must be provided with the schema of the dataset (defined in Section 4.2.2).
- GET /datasetManagement/schema/{schema_id}
Retrieves all information associated to a given schema, *schema_id*.
- DELETE /datasetManagement/schema/{schema_id}
Removes the schema identified by *schema_id*, and all datasets stored in the EGI DataHub platform.
- GET /datasetManagement/schemas
Returns the definition of the schemas stored and the identifier of each one. This operation provides the *schema_id* to request further information about a particular schema using the GET /datasetManagement/schema/{schema_id} operation.
- PUT /datasetManagement/dataset
It updates a dataset schema, *schema_id*, with the endpoint for retrieving the datasets.
- GET /datasetManagement/dataLake
Returns all available datasets associated to a given schema and stored in the EGI DataHub platform.
- GET /datasetManagement/dataset
Returns a particular dataset with a given schema, *schema_id*.

Policy Management REST API

The Policy Management subcomponent provides a REST API with twelve operations for the creation, retrieval, update, and deletion of policies. Figure 13 shows the Swagger interface that describes the API of each operation.

policymanagement Show/Hide List Operations Expand Operations

DELETE	/policymanagement/policy/{policy_id}	Deletes the information stored about the requested policy
GET	/policymanagement/policy/{policy_id}	Returns the stored information about the requested policy
PUT	/policymanagement/policy/{policy_id}	Updates a specify policy
GET	/policymanagement/policies/{area}	Returns the stored information about the requested policy
POST	/policymanagement/ai_model	Adds a new ai_model
GET	/policymanagement/ai_models	Returns the information of all the stored ai_models
GET	/policymanagement/ai_models/{policy_id}	Returns the information of all the stored ai_models for a particular policy
DELETE	/policymanagement/ai_model/{ai_model_id}	Deletes the information stored about the requested ai_model
GET	/policymanagement/ai_model/{ai_model_id}	Returns the stored information about the requested ai_model
PUT	/policymanagement/ai_model/{ai_model_id}	Updates a specify ai_model
GET	/policymanagement/policies	Returns the information of all the stored policies
POST	/policymanagement/policy	Adds a new policy

[BASE URL: /ai4pp] UPGRADE

Figure 13. Policy Management REST API

The operations are:

- POST /policymanagement/policy
Creates a new policy, the JSON schema described in Section 4.3.2 defines the parameters of this operation. The policy definition is stored in the database and an identifier is assigned.
- PUT /policymanagement/policy/{policy_id}
Updates a policy, the JSON schema described in Section 4.3.2 defines the parameters of this operation.
- GET /policymanagement/policy/{policy_id}
Returns all stored information about the requested policy.
- DELETE /policymanagement/policy/{policy_id}
Deletes the requested policy.
- GET /policymanagement/policies
Returns for all the stored policies the *policy_id*, name, owner, description, status, area, objective, list of datasets identifiers that are used within this policy and an identifier for that particular policy.
- GET /policymanagement/policies/{area}
Returns the information of all the policies for a particular area/pilot.
- POST /policymanagement/ai_model
Creates a new AI model, the JSON schema for the AI model is described in Section 4.3.2. The AI model definition is stored in the database and an identifier is assigned.
- PUT /policymanagement/ai_model/{ai_model_id}
Updates a new AI model, the JSON schema for the AI model is described in Section 4.3.2.
- GET /policymanagement/ai_model/{ai_model_id}
Returns the information stored about the requested AI model
- DELETE /policymanagement/ai_model/{ai_model_id}

- Deletes the specified AI model
- GET /policymanagement/ai_models
Returns for all the models stored the ai_model_id, name, description, aiAlgorithm, modelArtifact and url to obtain all the information of the ai_model.
- GET /policymanagement/ai_models/{policy_id}
Returns for all the models defined for a particular policy, the ai_model_id, name, description, aiAlgorithm, modelArtifact and an identifier of the ai_model.

4 Policy and Data Management Implementation

4.1 Policy and Data Management Component Architecture

The Policy and Data management component is made out of five components: the Web Interface, the Dataset Management component, the Policy Management component, a Database (DB) and EGI DataHub as depicted in Figure 14. The Web Interface allows non-technical users to define, update and use datasets and policies in an easy way through a set of web forms. The Dataset Management and the Policy Management components are in charge of the management of datasets and policies, respectively. The datasets, policies and AI models definitions are stored in a database. Finally, EGI DataHub is a remote file system provided by EGI based on EOSC that stores all AI4PublicPolicy dataset files.

Figure 14. Policy and Data Management Component Architecture

4.2 Dataset Management

The dataset management subcomponent provides all the necessary tools to define new datasets, upload and download data files from the AI4PP platform. A dataset is defined by its schema. All data files in a dataset have to respect the corresponding schema.

4.2.1 Dataset Management Architecture

The dataset management component is made out of four sub-components: a REST API, the dataset management subcomponent, a database and EGI DataHub. Figure 15 shows the sub-components and the interaction between them.

The REST API can be used by both end users and other components of the AI4PublicPolicy platform submitting CRUD operations on datasets. that will later be used by the different policies defined in the context of the project. The dataset management component handles all requests received through the REST API, stores the dataset schemas in a database and allows uploading and downloading datasets files stored in EGI DataHub. The database (DB in Figure 15), in this case MySQL, is used for storing the schemas of the datasets.

Figure 15. Dataset Management Subcomponent Architecture

4.2.2 Datasets Definition Persistence

Dataset schemas are defined or updated using the POST and PUT operations respectively, these operations receive as parameter a JSON object with this schema:

```
{
  "$schema": "https://json-schema.org/draft/2020-12/schema",
  "$id": "https://example.com/product.schema.json",
  "title": "Schema",
  "description": "Dataset schema",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "pilot": {
      "description": "The name of the pilot the dataset belongs to.",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "name": {
      "description": "Name of the dataset schema",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "sourceType": {
      "description": "The source type (csv, json, geojson, xlsx, image)",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "imageFormat": {
```

```

    "description": "The type of image in case the source type image has been selected (png, jpg)",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "description": {
    "description": "The description of the dataset",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "owner": {
    "description": "The owner of the dataset",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "language": {
    "description": "Language in which the dataset data is stored (English, Portuguese, Greek, Italian, Bulgarian)",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "schema": {
    "description": "Definition of the scheme fields",
    "type": "array",
    "items": {
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "name": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "description": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "type": {
          "type": "string"
        }
      },
      "defaultValue": {
        "type": "object"
      }
    },
    "uniqueItems": true
  }
}

```

```

}
},
"required": ["pilot", "name", "sourceType", "description", "owner"]
}

```

The JSON object is stored in the database (MySQL) to ensure persistence. The tables in the database that store the dataset schema are *dataset* and *field*. The *dataset* table stores the meta information associated to a given dataset: *name*, *source_type*, *owner*, *pilot*, *description*, *image_format*, and *language* provided in the JSON object. The *field* table stores the actual schema of the dataset, that is, the description of the different fields: *name*, *type*, *description*, *default_value* and *dataset_id*. Figure 16 shows the entity relationship diagram (ERD) of both tables, the dataset and parameter tables.

Figure 16. Dataset database entity relationship diagram

4.2.3 Datasets Persistence

When a dataset schema is defined, a directory is created in EGI DataHub. All datasets with that schema will be stored in that folder either using the PUT /datasetManagement/dataset operation or by uploading the files directly through EGI DataHub.

When a dataset is uploaded into EGI DataHub using the operation PUT operation, the dataset management component receives a notification, accesses the dataset and checks if the dataset satisfies the dataset schema. The Dataset Management component subscribes for changes into a particular EGI DataHub space to receive these events. Both, the process to configure the Dataset Management to access the AI4PublicPolicy EGI DataHub space and the process to subscribe to changes are explained in more detail in Section 4.2.3.1.

4.2.3.1 Integration with EGI DataHub

Accessing EGI DataHub from the Dataset Management component

To access the AI4PublicPolicy EGI DataHub space from the virtual machine where the Dataset Management component is running, a directory must be configured in the virtual machine¹.

First of all, a EGI DataHub client has to be downloaded and installed in the virtual machine:

```
curl -sS http://get.onedata.org/oneclient.sh | bash
```

¹ <https://docs.egi.eu/users/tutorials/vm-datahub/>

Then, a token and the domain of the EGI DataHub space provider is needed. The domain is the identifier of the file system space. The following steps are needed to obtain the token:

1. Log into the EGI DataHub web interface² (Figure 17~~Error! Reference source not found.~~):

Figure 17. EGI DataHub sing in web interface

2. Enter the token creation interface and click on the "Create new token" button (Figure 18):

Figure 18. EGI DataHub token interface

3. Click on the "ONECLIENT ACCESS" button (Figure 19):

² <https://datahub.egi.eu/ozw/onezone/i#/login>

Figure 19. EGI DataHub ONECLIENT ACCESS Interface

- Configure the token to be created by selecting the Access type, CAVEATCS REST and clicking the "Create token" button (Figure 20):

Figure 20. EGI DataHub Configure ONECLIENT ACCESS Token Interface

- This will generate a token like the one in Figure 21.

To configure the domain of the space provider, the next command must be executed in the shell or add it in the bash script:

```
export ONECLIENT_PROVIDER_HOST="elkh-cloud-ai4pp.datahub.egi.eu"
```

Once both the token and the domain are configured the following commands have to be executed in the shell. The first command creates the folder where the EGI DataHub space is going to be replicated and the second one configures the folder and replicates the space.

```
mkdir /tmp/space
```

```
oneclient /tmp/space
```

Subscription to changes

When the user uploads a dataset via EGI DataHub, the dataset management has to be informed that a new dataset has been added. For this purpose, EGI DataHub provides a REST API with a method³ that allows you to subscribe to changes. These changes can be either the creation or deletion of a new directory or file. The subscription request is handled through a HTTP connection.

While the connection remains open, changes will be received as soon as an event occurs in the space.

The HTTP request is as follows:

```
curl -N -H "X-Auth-Token: $TOKEN" \  
-X POST "https://$HOST/api/v3/oneprovider/changes/metadata/$SPACE_ID" \  
-H "Content-Type: application/json" -d "@./changes_req.json"
```

The \$TOKEN parameter is the string that allows the user to access a platform. In this case the token is required to grant access to our EGI DataHub account. The \$HOST parameter refers to the domain of the EGI DataHub space provider defined in the previous paragraphs.

The \$SPACE_ID parameter refers to the identifier of the AI4PublicPolicy space to be subscribed. Again, EGI DataHub web interface must be used to get the identifier. In the menu of the space, in this case "AI4PublicPolicy", access the file browser ("Data"). Then, select the folder DatasetManagement to get information about the changes, and click on the folder menu. Click on the "Information" option and a new window will open for this space identifier. Figure 24 and Figure 25 show this process.

³ https://onedata.org/#/home/api/stable/oneprovider?anchor=operation/get_space_changes

Figure 24. EGI DataHub Data Interface

Figure 25. EGI DataHub Space Information Interface

The Space ID must be included in the bash script or set in the shell using the following command:

```
export SPACE_ID="6006aa77ec1ed4cd68f2360396ef8715chc3f5"
```

Once all HTTP request parameters have been configured, the HTTP request can be executed.

Figure 26. EGI DataHub Test Folder Interface

```
$ curl -N -H "X-Auth-Token: $TOKEN" -X POST "https://$HOST/api/v3/oneprovider/change
s/metadatas/$SPACE_ID" -H "Content-Type: application/json" -d "@./changes_req.json"
{"seq":32144,"filePath":"/AI4PublicPolicy/DatasetManagement/TestMainDirectory/TestDirectory","fileMeta":{"rev":"1-0c53083ed34883de5952058bcf5d5878","mutators":
:["ca744ef96679d3da5df27672adf88d4dcha45e"],"fields":{"name":"TestDirectory"},"deleted":false,"changed":true},"fileId":"00000000052ADE16775696423383831363066
616564623639326663313364613966333231666262313139333863686636306423363030366161373765633165643463643638663233363033393665663837313563686336635"}
{"seq":32148,"filePath":"/AI4PublicPolicy/DatasetManagement/TestMainDirectory/TestDirectory/testFile.csv","fileMeta":{"rev":"1-1ff0a2888158f7ce04202520af658e3
a","mutators":["ca744ef96679d3da5df27672adf88d4dcha45e"],"fields":{"name":"testFile.csv"},"deleted":false,"changed":true},"fileId":"00000000052EC9F6775696423
31643632333308044439636466650838439623639373963366230366316443686636306423363030366161373765633165643463643638663233363033393665663837313563686336635"}
{"seq":32156,"filePath":"/AI4PublicPolicy/DatasetManagement/TestMainDirectory/TestDirectory/testFile.csv","fileMeta":{"rev":"3-e95ceb8a6f77b3e4dd9565055ff82cd"},"mutators":["ca744ef96679d3da5df27672adf88d4dcha45e"],"fields":{"name":"test
File.csv"},"deleted":true,"changed":true},"fileId":"00000000052EC9F677569642331643632333303064643963646665083843962363937396336623036631644368663630642336
3080366161373765633165643463643638663233363033393665663837313563686336635"}
{"seq":32166,"filePath":"/AI4PublicPolicy/DatasetManagement/TestMainDirectory/TestDirectory/testFile.csv","fileMeta":{"rev":"4-cc55d26ea53f1a3e7c3e13c6c7e84036"},"mutators":["ca744ef96679d3da5df27672adf88d4dcha45e"],"fields":{"name":"Test
Directory@0810faedb692fc13da9f321fbb11938chf68d"},"deleted":true,"changed":true},"fileId":"00000000052ADE16775696423383831363066616564623639326663313364613
966333231666262313139333863686636306423363030366161373765633165643463643638663233363033393665663837313563686336635"}

```

Figure 27. Subscriber Output

Analysing the event generated by the subscriber when the "TestDirectory" folder is created (blue lines in Figure 27), the event provides the path where the folder has been created, the name of the folder created, a Boolean indicating whether the folder has been created or deleted and the folder identifier. This information is obtained for each change made in the AI4PublicPolicy space.

```
{ "seq":32144, "filePath":"/AI4PublicPolicy/DatasetManagement/TestMainDirectory/Te
stDirectory", "fileMeta":{"rev":"1-
0c53083ed34883de5952058bcf5d5878", "mutators":["ca744ef96679d3da5df27672adf88d4dc
ha45e"], "fields":{"name":"TestDirectory"},"deleted":false, "changed":true}, "fileI
d":"00000000052ADE1677569642338383136306661656462363932666331336461396633323166
62623131393338636866363064233630303661613737656331656434636436386632333630333936
65663837313563686336635"}

```

4.3 Policy Management

The policy management subcomponent provides operations needed to define, update and delete policies.

4.3.1 Policy Management Architecture

The policy management subcomponent is made out of three sub-components: the REST API, the policy management subcomponent and a database, as depicted in Figure 28. The REST API provides CRUD operations to interact with the policy management subcomponent. The policy management component handles requests from the REST API and stores, updates, reads, or deletes policies and AI models. The policies are stored in a MySQL database.

Figure 28. Policy Management Component Architecture

4.3.2 Policy Management Data Persistence

Policies and AI Models are defined or updated using the POST and PUT operations, respectively. Both operations need as parameter a JSON object with a given schema.

The Policy JSON schema:

```
{
  "$schema": "https://json-schema.org/draft/2020-12/schema",
  "$id": "https://example.com/product.schema.json",
  "title": "Policy",
  "description": "Policy definition",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "area": {
      "description": "The name of the pilot for which the policy has been defined",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "name": {
      "description": "Name of the policy",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "objective": {
      "description": "The name of the pilot for which the policy has been defined",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "description": {
      "description": "The description of the dataset",

```

```

    "type": "string"
  },
  "owner": {
    "description": "The owner of the datasets",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "KPI": {
    "description": "Definition of the policy KPIs",
    "type": "array",
    "items": {
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "name": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "value": {
          "type": "string"
        }
      },
      "uniqueItems": true
    }
  },
  "metadata": {
    "description": "Definition of the policy Metadata",
    "type": "array",
    "items": {
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "version": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "category": {
          "type": "object"
        }
      },
      "uniqueItems": true
    }
  }
}

```

```

    }
  },
  "datasetsId": {
    "description": "The identifiers of the datasets to be used in the policy",
    "type": "array",
    "items": {
      "type": "integer",
      "uniqueItems": true
    }
  }
},
"required": [ "area", "name", "objective", "description", "owner" ]
}

```

The AI Model JSON schema:

```

{
  "$schema": "https://json-schema.org/draft/2020-12/schema",
  "$id": "https://example.com/product.schema.json",
  "title": "ai_model",
  "description": "AI Model definition",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "policyId": {
      "description": "The identifier of the policy where the model is going to be used",
      "type": "integer"
    },
    "name": {
      "description": "Name of the policy",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "description": {
      "description": "The description of the dataset",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "ai_algorithm": {
      "description": "The owner of the datasets",
      "type": "string"
    }
  }
}

```

```

},
"model_artifact": {
  "description": "The owner of the datasets",
  "type": "string"
},
"domain": {
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "input": {
      "type": "object"
    },
    "output": {
      "type": "object"
    }
  },
  "description": {
    "type": "string"
  },
  "type": {
    "type": "string"
  }
},
"metadata": {
  "description": "Definition of the policy Metadata",
  "type": "array",
  "items": {
    "type": "object",
    "properties": {
      "version": {
        "type": "string"
      },
      "category": {
        "type": "object"
      }
    }
  },
  "uniqueItems": true
}

```

```
},  
"learned_parameters": {  
  "description": "The parameters used by the model",  
  "type": "array",  
  "items": {  
    "type": "object",  
    "properties": {  
      "name": {  
        "type": "string"  
      },  
      "type": {  
        "type": "string"  
      },  
      "value": {  
        "type": "string"  
      }  
    },  
    "uniqueItems": true  
  }  
},  
"workflow": {  
  "type": "object",  
  "properties": {  
    "name": {  
      "type": "string"  
    },  
    "application": {  
      "type": "string"  
    },  
    "source": {  
      "type": "string"  
    },  
    "source_type": {  
      "type": "string"  
    }  
  }  
},
```

```

    "description": {
      "type": "string"
    }
  },
},
"required": ["policyId", "name", "description"]
}

```

When the policy management subcomponent receives a request to create or update a policy or AI model, it processes the JSON file and stores the information persistently in the MySQL database. Figure 29 shows the entity relationship diagram of the tables used for the definition of a policy. Figure 30 shows the entities involved in the definition of an AI model. In total there are nine tables: *policy*, *policy_datasets*, *policy_metadata* and *KPI*, for the policy definition, and *ai_model*, *domain*, *ai_model_metadata*, *workflow* and *learned_parameters*, for the AI model. To associate the datasets to the policy an extra table, *policy_datasets*, is defined. This table stores the *policy_id* and the *dataset_id*. Both models, the policy and AI model, were defined in deliverable D2.3 - Definition and Specification of Policy-Related Datasets.

Figure 29. Policy Database Entity Relationship Diagram

Figure 30. AI Model Database Entity Relationship Diagram

4.4 Policy and Data Management Sequence Diagrams

This section presents the sequence diagrams that show the interaction between the user and the different sub-components of the Policy and Dataset Management component. Definition of a Dataset Schema.

Figure 31 shows the sequence diagram when a user defines a new dataset schema.

1. The user accesses the form provided by the web interface to define a new dataset schema.
- 2-6. The user indicates the area, the dataset schema name, the description, owner, source type, and language.
7. If the source type is an image, the user indicates the image type (7.a), otherwise it defines the fields of the schema.
8. The request is submitted and sent to the Dataset Management subcomponent:
 - 8.1. The web interface creates the schema object.
 - 8.2. The web interface sends the POST request to the Dataset Management subcomponent.
 - 8.2.1. The Dataset Management stores the dataset schema into the database.
 - 8.2.1. The Dataset Management creates a folder for the dataset schema in to the EGI DataHub.
 - 8.3 The web interface informs that the dataset schema has been stored.

Figure 31. Definition of a Dataset Schema

4.4.1 Update a Dataset Schema

Figure 32 shows the sequence diagram for updating a dataset schema.

1. The user accesses the web interface to define a new dataset schema.
- 2-3. The user indicates the area and the dataset schema.
4. The web interface sends a GET request to the Dataset Management subcomponent to read all information related to dataset schema and fills in the form with that information.
- 5-8. The user updates the description, owner, source type, language, image type or fields.
9. The requests is submitted and sent to the Dataset Management subcomponent:
 - 9.1. The web interface creates the schema object.
 - 9.2. The web interface sends the PUT request to the Dataset Management component.

9.2.1. The Dataset Management checks if the changes satisfy the schema of the datasets stored in the EGI DataHub.

9.2.2a. The Dataset Management updates the dataset schema in the database.

9.2.3a. The Dataset Management updates the folder of the dataset schema in the EGI DataHub.

Figure 32. Updating a Dataset Schema

4.4.2 Retrieve a Dataset Schema

Figure 33 **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the sequence diagram for retrieving all data stored about a particular dataset schema.

2. The user accesses the web interface to show dataset schema information.
- 2-3. The user indicates the area and the dataset schema.
4. The requests is submitted and sent to the Dataset Management component:
 - 4.1. The web interface gets the dataset schema identifier (*schema_id*).
 - 4.2. The web interface sends the GET request to the Dataset Management component.
 - 4.2.1. The Dataset Management requests the dataset schema information to the database.
 - 4.3 The web interface depicts all information into the dataset schema interface.

Figure 33. Dataset Schema Retrieval

4.4.3 Delete a Dataset Schema

Figure 34 shows the sequence diagram to delete a particular dataset schema.

1. The user accesses the web interface to delete a particular dataset.
- 2-3. The user indicates the area and the dataset.
4. The requests is submitted and sent to the Dataset Management subcomponent:
 - 4.1. The web interface gets the dataset identifier (*dataset_id*)
 - 4.2. The web interface sends the DELETE request to the Dataset Management subcomponent.

4.2.1. The Dataset Management deletes the dataset stored in the database.

4.2.2. The Dataset Management deletes all dataset files stored in the dataset folder at EGI DataHub

4.3 The web interface informs that the dataset has been deleted.

Figure 34. Dataset Schema Delete Operation

4.4.4 List of Datasets

Figure 35 shows the sequence diagram to list all available dataset files for a particular dataset schema.

1. The user accesses the web interface to delete a given data schema.
- 2-3. The user indicates the area and the dataset.
4. The requests is submitted and sent to the Dataset Management subcomponent:
 - 4.1. The web interface sends the GET request to the Dataset Management subcomponent.
 - 4.1.1. The Dataset Management obtains the EGI DataHub directory where the files are stored.
 - 4.1.2. The Dataset Management gets all dataset files stored in the dataset folder at EGI DataHub.
 - 4.2 The web interface depicts all available dataset files from the requested dataset schema.

Figure 35. List of Datasets

4.4.5 Upload a Dataset File

Figure 36 shows the sequence diagram to upload a dataset file for a particular dataset schema.

1. The user accesses the web interface to upload a particular policy.
- 2-4. The user indicates the area, the dataset and the endpoint where the dataset is available.
5. The requests is sent to the Dataset Management subcomponent:
 - 5.1. The web interface sends the PUT request to the Dataset Management subcomponent.
 - 5.1.1. The Dataset Management obtains the EGI DataHub directory where the dataset files are stored.
 - 5.1.2. The Dataset Management subcomponent downloads the dataset file.
 - 5.1.3. The Dataset Management uploads the file in the dataset folder at EGI DataHub.
 - 5.2 The web interface informs the user that the dataset file has been uploaded.

Figure 36. Uploading a Dataset

4.4.6 Download a Dataset File

Figure 37 shows the sequence diagram to download a dataset file with a given schema.

1. The user selects the dataset file listed.
 - 1.1. The web interface sends the GET request to the Dataset Management subcomponent.
 - 1.2.1. The Dataset Management obtains the EGI DataHub directory where the dataset files are stored.
 - 1.2.2. The Dataset Management retrieves the dataset file.
 - 1.2.3. The Dataset Management sends the file.

Figure 37. Downloading a Dataset

4.4.7 Policy Definition

Figure 38 shows the sequence diagram to define a new policy.

1. The user defines the policy information in the form provided by the web interface to define a new dataset schema.
- 2-9. The user indicates the area, the policy name, the description, the objective, owner, datasets, KPIs and metadata.
10. The request is submitted and sent to the Policy Management component:
 - 10.1. The web interface creates the policy object.
 - 10.2. The web interface sends the POST request to the Policy Management subcomponent.
 - 10.2.1. The Policy Management stores the policy into the database.

Figure 38. Policy Definition

4.4.8 Update a Policy

Figure 39 shows the sequence diagram to update a policy.

1. The user accesses the form provided by the web interface to update a policy.
- 2-3. The user indicates the area and the policy.
4. The Web Interface sends a GET request to the Policy Management to read all information about the policy and fills in the form with that information.
- 5-10. The user updates the description, the objective, owner, datasets, KPIs and metadata.

11. The requests is submitted and sent to the Policy Management component:
 - 11.1. The web interface creates the policy object.
 - 11.2. The web interface sends the PUT request to the Policy Management component.
 - 11.2.1. The Policy Management updates the policy information in the database.

Figure 39. Updating a Policy

4.4.9 Retrieve a Policy

Figure 40 shows the sequence diagram to retrieve all data stored for a policy.

1. The user accesses the web interface to show policy information.
- 2-4 . The user indicates the area and the policy.
5. The requests is submitted and sent to the Policy Management component:
 - 5.1. The web interface gets the policy identifier (*policy_id*).
 - 5.2. The web interface sends the GET request to the Policy Management component.
 - 5.2.1. The Policy Management request the policy information to the database.
 - 5.3 The web interface depicts all information of the policy.

Figure 40. Policy Retrieval

4.4.10 Delete a Policy

Figure 41 shows the sequence diagram to delete a given policy.

1. The user accesses the web interface to delete a particular policy.
- 2-3. The user indicates the area and the policy.
4. The requests is submitted and sent to the Policy Management component:
 - 4.1. The web interface gets the policy identifier (*policy_id*)
 - 4.2. The web interface sends the DELETE request to the Policy Management component.
 - 4.2.1. The Policy Management deletes the policy stored in the database.
 - 4.3 The web interface informs that the policy has been deleted.

Figure 41. Policy Deletion

4.4.11 AI Model Definition

Figure 42 shows the sequence diagram to define a new AI model.

1. The user accesses the web interface to define a new AI Model.
- 2-11. The user indicates the area, the policy name, the AI model name, the description, the AI algorithm, model artifact, domain, learned parameters, workflow and metadata.
12. The requests is submitted and sent to the Policy Management component:
 - 12.1. The web interface creates the AI model object.
 - 12.2. The web interface sends the POST request to the Policy Management component.
 - 12.2.1. The Policy Management stores the AI model into the database.

Figure 42. AI Model Definition

4.4.12 Update an AI Model

Figure 43 shows the sequence diagram to update an AI model.

1. The user accesses the web interface to update an AI model.
- 2-4. The user indicates the area, the policy and the AI model.

5. The Web Interface sends a GET request to the Policy Management to obtain all information about the policy and fills in the form with that information.
- 6-12. The user updates the description, the AI algorithm, model artifact, domain, learned parameters, workflow and metadata.
13. The requests is submitted and sent to the Policy Management component:
 - 13.1. The web interface creates the ai model object.
 - 13.2. The web interface sends the PUT request to the Policy Management component.
 - 13.2.1. The Policy Management updates the AI model stored in the database.

Figure 43. Updating an AI Model

4.4.13 Retrieve an AI Model

Figure 44 shows the sequence diagram to retrieve all data stored about a particular AI Model.

2. The user accesses the web interface to show AI Model information.
- 2-4. The user indicates the area, the policy and the AI Model.
5. The requests is submitted and sent to the Policy Management component:
 - 5.1. The web interface gets the AI Model identifier (*ai_model_id*)
 - 5.2. The web interface sends the GET request to the Policy Management component
 - 5.2.1. The Policy Management request the AI Model information to the database
 - 5.3 The web interface depicts all information into the AI model interface

Figure 44. AI Model Retrieval

4.4.14 Delete an AI Model

Figure 45 shows the sequence diagram to delete an AI Model.

1. The user accesses the web interface to show the AI Model information.
- 2-5. The user indicates the area, the policy and the AI Model.
5. The requests is sent to the Policy Management component:
 - 5.1. The web interface gets the AI Model identifier (*ai_model_id*)

5.2. The web interface sends the DELETE request to the Policy Management component.

5.2.1. The Policy Management deletes the AI Model stored in the database.

5.3 The web interface informs that the AI Model has been deleted.

Figure 45. Deleting an AI Model

5 Policy and Data Management Software Distribution

The Policy and Data Management component can be deployed through the Linux distribution zip file. The Policy and Data Management component can be deployed as an independent component of the VPME. This component requires access to EGI DataHub to store the datasets and to configure the Dataset Management subcomponent to subscribe to events and have remote access.

5.1 Linux Distribution

The Policy and Data Management component runs on Linux environments. It requires Java 1.8.x or a higher version. The distribution zip file is available at <https://dl.lsdupm.ovh/Projects/AI4PP/dataManagement-2.0.0-docker.zip>

Configuration

The conf/configParams.sh file must be updated with the IP address where the service will be available, the location of the datastore and other information for configuring the database.

- DATASET_MANAGEMENT_HOST, DATASET_MANAGEMENT_PORT, POLICY_MANAGEMENT_HOST, POLICY_MANAGEMENT_PORT, WEBINTERFACE_HOST, WEBINTERFACE_PORT corresponds to the IP and port where the webservice will be running.
- DB_IP and DB_PORT indicates where the database is running.
- DB_NAME configures the name of the database.
- DB_USER and DB_PASS gives access to the database.
- ONEDATA_TOKEN the token used to interact with EGI DataHub.

Execution Models

The Policy and Data Management component can run in a single node (standalone version). The next commands show how to start and stop the Policy and Data Management component in standalone mode:

```
#The Data Management distribution is unzipped. The commands are executed in the folder where the distribution is unzipped

#1. Installation
#It configures the database connection parameters
$ cd bin; ./install_data_management.sh

#2. Start the Data Management
$ ./start_data_management.sh

#3. Stop the Data Management
$ ./stop_data_management.sh
```

6 Conclusions

This deliverable is the second and last version of the component in charge of policies and data management. This is a central component in the AI4PublicPolicy platform used by the VPME (the front-end of the platform) and other components that need access to policies, datasets and AI models. This is a demonstrator deliverable that presents the Policy and Data Management architecture, its internals, how it is deployed and how it can be used by technical and non-technical users. The REST API and the sequence diagrams that document the component usage and implementation have been presented. The software is available to be downloaded and used as an application running under a Linux environment or as Docker image.

The associated task (T3.1) completed at month M18. However, some changes may be required to fulfil the pilot requirements and for its integration with the VPME whose development will continue during the next months.